

Evaluation of the modus operandi

The modus operandi has been developed during the first EUPHRESCO ERA-Net and aims to be a guidance document for a long term self sustainable network of funders of plant health research. As EUPHRESCO II aims too, to establish such a long term network, the evaluation and amendment of the modus operandi is an important aspect.

This questionnaire inquires necessary changes or enhancements in the current modus operandi.

Please note, that this questionnaire does currently not regard the possible connection of EUPHRESCO and EPPO. This aspect will be considered separately

Network purpose

Q1: The modus operandi notes the NETWORK PURPOSE (page 8) in three paragraphs. Please, read the paragraphs.

Do you agree with purposes mentioned there?

Yes, I fully agree

Yes, I agree but I would like to add

No, I do not agree; please make the following changes

Other Additional comments:

Network coordination

The modus operandi describes possible network coordination on page 9 to 11.

Q2: In the current draft, a network steering group is planned. This will consist of the network coordinator, the network secretariat and a network management group (see page 9 in modus operandi).

Do you agree that a kind of steering group will be necessary?

Yes, a steering group will be necessary

No, I don't think the network needs a steering group (please give your reasons)

If you ticked YES, please answer the following:

All three positions will be necessary

I think the steering group should only consist of

Network Coordinator

Network Secretariat

Network management group

Q3: Could you (or any other person in your organisation) take over a role in the steering group for a certain time (e.g. 3 years)?

Yes, no problem

Probably yes, depending on the workload

Can't say at the moment

No, surely not

If you just ticked No, please give the reasons, why it will not be possible

Q4: Members of the network are referred to as 'partners'. The membership is restricted to research funders (programme owners or managers) of phytosanitary research in Europe, including potentially other such bodies in third countries (as appropriate). Are you content with this definition?

Yes, I am content with this definition

No, I would like to have this part changed or amended in the following way

In addition to the partners, the modus operandi allows for **observers** (Organisations, official bodies and institutions with an interest in plant health who are not full partners (principally, but not exclusively, research programme owners or managers) that may wish to join the network in the future, or be linked to its activities) and **advisors** (organisations which influence plant health policy and with decision makers which need to have an input into the network's activities, i.e. to ensure that trans-national phytosanitary research best serves the needs of plant health policy and is policy led).

Q5: Do you agree that observers and advisors a part of the network as defined above?

- Yes, they should be part of the future network
- No, I don't think they should be part of the network
- Can't say at the moment

If you just ticked No, can you give some reasons for your decision?

If you just ticked Yes, please consider which organisations you would see important as

a) Observers

- Plant health organisations which are research funders but are not partner in the network
- Plant health organisations which are not research funders
- Organisations which are not directly plant health organisations, e.g. from third countries
- Others?

b) Advisors

- EU-Commission
- EPPO
- EFSA
- Others?

The term **stakeholder** refers to anybody with an interest in plant health who is not a partner of the network (e.g. governmental organisations, research institutes or commercial organisations, or specific individuals or scientists). Some stakeholders might become partners of the network, if fulfilling the above mentioned criteria (under vii above). Commercial organisations and firms can't become network partners but might participate in trans-national projects or other activities if appropriate (e.g. provision of funds or in-kind contributions).

Q6: Do you agree, with the above definition of stakeholders and their part in the network?

Yes, I agree

No, I don't agree

If you just ticked No, please explain your critics or alternative definition and ideas.

Network administration

The modus operandi describes the NETWORK ADMINISTRATION on page 11 to 13.

Meetings are assessed as an important part of the network. They could take place once a year, rotating between the partners. Performance of meetings and the participation of partners have to be financed out of own resources.

Q7: Do you consider meetings a necessary tool for network communication?

Yes, I do consider meetings as an important tool

No, I don't think meetings are necessary

I consider meetings necessary in certain cases (please specify)

If you just ticked Yes, please consider:

a) Would you be able to hold such a meeting as a host?

Yes

No

Can't say at the moment

b) Would you/your organisation be able to finance the participation in meetings (personnel, travel costs etc.)?

Yes

No

Can't say at the moment

Q8: Alternatively, electronic communication tools could be used to ensure necessary contact between the partners. Please tick the preferred communication tools (you can tick more than one):

Email

Phone conference

Video conference

Google spreadsheets (or similar)

Chat box via the homepage

Interactive homepage

Other, please specify

Q9: Do you have experiences with such electronic tools?

Yes, e.g.

No

Q10: Decisions on routine issues should be made by the steering group and send for information to all partners. Do you agree to that?

Yes, I agree

No, I do not agree

I can't say at the moment

If you just ticked No, what is the alternative?

Decisions should generally be made by all partners

Decisions should be proposed by the steering group but send to all partners for agreement

Others, please specify

Q11: Contact to the advisors is noted as task of the steering group. Do you agree to that?

Yes, I agree

No, I do not agree

I can't say at the moment

If you just ticked No, please explain

Q12: The following tasks are considered necessary aspects of the network administration and therefore under the responsibility of the steering group. Please tick which of them you consider necessary.

Maintenance of the common strategic research agenda

Maintenance of the database on national phytosanitary research projects

Maintenance of the homepage

Advising the EU-commission on plant health topics relevant for EU funding in the framework programmes

Evaluation of the network activities after an agreed period of time

Linkages to other organisations (e.g. USDA, CABI), ERA-Nets, Networks of Excellence, third countries etc.

Others, please specify

Please note, that the paragraphs about the INITIATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF TRANS-NATIONAL PROJECTS (page 13 to 15) are not part of this evaluation!

Supplementing documents

Q13: Documents are noted on page 15 to 16, which are considered to be necessary for the future network. These contain the Network COLLABORATION AGREEMENT and the Network LETTER OF INTENT by the partners. Do you consider such documents helpful or necessary?

Collaboration agreement

- Yes, this would be necessary
- Yes, this would be helpful, but not necessary
- No, this is neither necessary nor helpful

If you just ticked No, please explain

Letter of Intent

- Yes, this would be necessary
- Yes, this would be helpful, but not necessary
- No, this is neither necessary nor helpful

If you just ticked No, please explain

Alternatively, I would recommend the following documents

Additional comments

Please, send the filled in evaluation form back to Silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de until May 18th!

AGES (Sylvia) SASA (David Kenyon) DASTI (Niels Gotke?) MMM-FI (Tuula)

Q1: The modus operandi notes the Network Purpose (page 8) in three paragraphs. Please, read the paragraphs. Do you agree with purposes mentioned there?

Yes, I fully agree	x	x		x
Yes I agree but would like to add			x in iii add: upcomming pests	

No, I do not agree, please make the following changes
Other comments

Q2: In the current draft, a network steering group is planned. This will consist of the network coordinator, the network secretariat and a network management group (see page 9 in modus operandi). Do you agree that a kind of steering group will be necessary?

Yes, a steering group will be necessary	x	x	x	x
No, I don't think the network needs a steering group (please give your reasons)				

If you ticked YES, please answer the following:

All three positions will be necessary	x	x	x	x
I think the steering group should only consist of				
Network Coordinator				
Network Secretariat				
Network management group				

Q3: Could you (or any other person in your organisation) take over a role in the steering group for a certain time (e.g. 3 years)?

Yes, no problem				
Probably yes, depending on the workload	x	x		x
Can't say at the moment			x	
No, surely not				

If you just ticked No, please give the reasons, why it will not be possible

Q4: Members of the network are referred to as 'partners'. The membership is restricted to research funders (programme owners or managers) of phytosanitary r

Yes, I am content with this definition	x	x	x	
No, I would like to have this part changed or amended in the following way				x If commercial organisations and firms can't become network partners (I cannot recall the reason), Then definition of partner should be changed accordingly as commercial companies and firms may have phytosanitary research programmes especially for regulated non-quarantine pests which are under the scope of EUPHRESKO

Q5: Do you agree that observers and advisors a part of the network as defined above?

Yes, they should be part of the future network	x	x	x	x
No, I don't think they should be part of the network				
Can't say at the moment				
If you just ticked No, can you give some reasons for your decision?				
If you just ticked Yes, please consider which organisations you would see important as				

a) Observers

Plant health organisations which are research funders but are not partner in the network	x	x	x	x
Plant health organisations which are not research funders	x	x	x	x
Organisations which are not directly plant health organisations, e.g. from third countries				

NPPS Netherlands (Paul)	FPS Belgium (Ria)	INIA Spain (Pilar)	FGU VNIKR Russia (Nathalia)	INRA France (Thierry)	MARA-GDAR Türkei (Alev)	MARDD Estonia)Küllü	BMLFUW Austria (Elfriede)	DAFF Irland (James)
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x Paragraph 3: regulated (Q and non-Q) pests, including emerging pests and non-native invasive species (iso plants in the environment)	x ii: and avoid research duplication iii: resulting in the maintenance of the EU competitiveness	x i the concept of "third countries" should be clarified iii The sentence "the overarching aim is to help protect Europe's agriculture, horticulture, and forestry from regulated plant pests, as well as plants in the environment, through effective trans-national research collaboration is not clear enough. It should be related quarantine/statutory plant health and emerging plant pests.	x	x	x	x	x	x In paragraph iii. The network should also be concerned with non-regulated but potentially harmful plant pests (i.e. new threats)
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x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
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	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

x

x

x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
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x currently there are no resources available for this. The workload is already high and no additional staff is planned

Research in x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x
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x The membership is restricted to research funders (programme owners or managers) of phytosanitary research in Europe, including potentially other such funding bodies in third countries (as appropriate)

x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
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x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

	x		x	x	x	x	x	x
	x		x					x

Others?

b) Advisors

EU-Commission
 EPPO
 EFSA
 Others?

x	x	x	x	
x	x	x	x	
x	x		x	
		x COPHS, SCPH		x as indicated in the text

Q6: Do you agree, with the above definition of stakeholders and their part in the network?

Yes, I agree

No, I don't agree

If you just ticked No, please explain your critics or alternative definition and ideas.

x	x	x		
				x
				Look at the commentarie at Q4

Q7: Do you consider meetings a necessary tool for network communication?

Yes, I do consider meetings as an important tool

No, I don't think meetings are necessary

I consider meetings necessary in certain cases (please specify)

		x	x	x
x				

1. For development of topics for common research agenda
 2. For decision taking about project proposals

If you just ticked Yes, please consider:

a) Would you be able to hold such a meeting as a host?

Yes

No

Can't say at the moment

x	x	x	x	

b) Would you/your organisation be able to finance the participation in meetings (personnel, travel costs etc.)?

Yes

No

Can't say at the moment

		x	x	
x				x

Q8: Alternatively, electronic communication tools could be used to ensure necessary contact between the partners. Please tick the preferred communication too

Email

Phone conference

Video conference

Google spreadsheets (or similar)

Chat box via the homepage

Interactive homepage

Other, please specify

x	x	x	x
x	x	x	
	x	x	x
x		x	x
		x	
x			x

Q9: Do you have experiences with such electronic tools?

Yes, e.g.

x all those ticked	x	x listed above	x
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Observers could be part of the network but should not be involved with decisions, which should be the exclusive right of the network partners (funders)

x	x		x		x	x	x	x
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x

x COPHS, NNPO, SCPH, SCAR, other research (funding) networks

x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
Stakeholders could play an important role in supporting a particular project but not as a network partner nor observer or advisor	Stakeholders who might become partners should rather be involved as OBSERVERS instead of stakeholders	According with the definition of observers and advisors, we think that the definition should be clarified. "The term stakeholder refers to anybody with an interest in plant health who is not a partner of the network neither observer or advisor (e.g. governmental organisations, research institutes or commercial organisations, or specific individuals or scientists)"						Comment- If a stakeholder is going to contribute money to the network, I think they should have equal rights to partners. My impression from the last meeting was that at EU level, greater inclusion of commercial interests was viewed as desirable.

x	x	x			x	x		x
			x One general meeting a year	x I would prefer as few meetings as possible and rather use videoconferences or other communication tools that do not imply travel		x identification of research topics (needs, goals, priorities); results of evaluation-decision, implementation and monitoring		x For development of topics for common research agenda For decision taking about project proposals

x					x	x	x	x
	x	x	x					

x	x	x			x	x	x	x
			x	x		x	x	

Is (you can tick more than one):

x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
x			x	x		x	x	
x	x	x		x				
x		x			x	x		x
	x Web conference	x evo.caltech.edu/						x

x video and phone conference	x e-mail = ok phone conference: not suitable when group is too large and if not strictly directed	x it is free and really useful	x email and phone conference	x Video conferences, teleconference ...	x Email and google spreadsheets	x	x	x
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No

Q10: Decisions on routine issues should be made by the steering group and send for information to all partners. Do you agree to that?

Yes, I agree	x		x		x
	x please specify what routine issues could be				

No, I do not agree

I can't say at the moment

If you just ticked No, what is the alternative?

Decisions should generally be made by all partners

Decisions should be proposed by the steering group but send to all partners for agreement

Others, please specify

Q11: Contact to the advisors is noted as task of the steering group. Do you agree to that?

Yes, I agree	x		x		x
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No, I do not agree

I can't say at the moment

If you just ticked No, please explain

Q12: The following tasks are considered necessary aspects of the network administration and therefore under the responsibility of the steering group. Please tick

Maintenance of the common strategic research agenda	x		x		x
Maintenance of the database on national phytosanitary research projects	x		x		x
Maintenance of the homepage	x	x	x	x	x
Advising the EU-commission on plant health topics relevant for EU funding in the framework programmes	x	x	x	x	x
Evaluation of the network activities after an agreed period of time	x	x	x	x	x
Linkages to other organisations (e.g. USDA, CABI), ERA-Nets, Networks of Excellence, third countries etc.	x		x		x

Others, please specify

Q13: Documents are noted on page 15 to 16, which are considered to be necessary for the future network. These contain the Network collaboration agreement necessary?

Collaboration agreement

Yes, this would be necessary			x		x
Yes, this would be helpful, but not necessary	x	x			
No, this is neither necessary nor helpful					

If you just clicked no, please explain

Letter of Intent

Yes, this would be necessary	x				x
Yes, this would be helpful, but not necessary		x		x	
No, this is neither necessary nor helpful					

Alternatively, I would recommend the following documents

See page 15/16 of Modus operandi, e.g. toolbox documents, dependent on size of projects

x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x although this is a leading question
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x

x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
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Yes in terms of general direction and policy and always with the Comm and possibly EFSA but in addition I think that for individual projects, the coordinator should have the latitude to inform the advisors, especially EPPO, of specific issues which may be of interest to them.

k which of them you consider necessary.

	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

x Call management and dissemination activities (newsletter etc.)

and the Network letter of intent by the partners. Do you consider such documents helpful or

	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
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x A formal/legal/binding document do not guarantee the continuity of a network. EUPHRESCO unifies professional volunteers who benefit of being a network	x A document not legal has no sense. The Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement are enough
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x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
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x A document not legal has no sense. The Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement are enough

A letter of intent expresses the willingness of collaboration and that is OK. At a project level legal binding documents are necessary, especially for EP and VP funding mechanisms

See page 15/16 of Modus operandi, e.g. toolbox documents; dependent on size of projects

Comment- in terms of securing funds for meetings etc the above documents are valuable as they represent an official commitment.

Additional comments

Q10 Perhaps routine
issues could be defined

The aim is that EUPHRESKO should continue as a self sustainable long-term network of phytosanitary research funders after 2013. Taking into account our reply in Q3 we would like to indicate that long term structures should be provided for administration and coordination. Investigating opportunities (on financing, infrastructure, involvement of (additional) stakeholders, further involvement of advisors and

Perhaps one should also define the responsibilities of the Partners in relation to activities in their own countries. Suggestions include:
Organise an annual meeting on plant health research
Maintain and update a national phytosanitary research agenda
Co-ordinate the collection and review of research topics for submission
Maintain a national register of plant health organisations, researchers, expertise poss through EPPO
Dissemination of EUPHRESKO activities etc

EUPHRESCO II

Modus operandi

**Principles for a self-sustainable, long-term network
of phytosanitary (statutory plant health) research
funders and programmes managers**

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Draft

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<http://www.euphresco.org>

Version: November 2013

Introduction

The ERA-Net Project EUPHRESKO II is the continuance of EUPHRESKO, a policy-led coordination action, initiated by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS). The 3-year project started in January 2011, funded from the EU 7th framework programme. EUPHRESKO stands for **E**uropean **P**hytosanitary **R**esearch **C**ooperation and connects phytosanitary (statutory plant health) research funders (programme owners or managers) from 22 countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and the UK.

The aim of the EUPHRESKO projects was to coordinate phytosanitary research at the European level. This involved coordination and co-operation between nationally-based phytosanitary research programmes in Europe for the first time through networking of research activities and a potential mutual opening or collaboration between national programmes. This coordination of national research has not been done significantly before EUPHRESKO nor has there been any significant trans-national funding of research, nor any alignment with EU-funded plant health research. EUPHRESKO therefore combines three main goals:

- Develop phytosanitary research policy and coordination at the EU-wide level.
- Optimise the research provision that underpins EU quarantine plant health policy development and implementation by reducing duplication and pooling resources.
- Increase the capacity of European phytosanitary science and research, in order to prevent the disappearance of EU expertise and maintain Europe's competitiveness in the global market. This supports EPPO's declaration of a *State of Emergency in Plant Health* in Madeira in 2004.

The projects were fully supported by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers for Plant Health Services (COPHS), The European Commission's Directorate General for Health and Consumer Protection (DG SANCO), the European Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), all of which have European plant health responsibilities.

One component of the work plan of EUPHRESKO and EUPHRESKO II was the establishment of a self-sustainable, long-term cooperation network in Europe to ensure a durable coordination of European phytosanitary research. The initial basis for such a cooperation initiative has already been established through EUPHRESKO's activities since 2006.

Scope of the document

This Modus Operandi describes the organisation and the main functions of the long-term cooperation initiative EUPHRESKO. The network will represent the transformation of the EU financed EUPHRESKO ERA-Net into a self-sustainable network of interested partners. The document represents the proposed principles that will be necessary to initiate, operate and maintain a durable and self-sustainable network of phytosanitary research funders in Europe.

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Definition of terms

Applied research	Original investigation undertaken in order to acquire new knowledge. It is, however, directed primarily towards a specific practical aim or objective support system
Basic/fundamental research	Experimental or theoretical work undertaken primarily to acquire new knowledge of the underlying foundation of phenomena and observable facts, without any particular application or use in view
Database	A collection of independent works, data or other materials which are arranged in a systematic or methodical way and are individually accessible by electronic or other means.
ERA-Net	European Research Area – Networking, element of the FP6 specific programme aiming at integration and strengthening the European Research Area via coordination and mutual opening of national and regional research programmes
EUPHRESCO	EC sixth framework programme ERA-Net project entitled ‘European Phytosanitary (statutory plant health) Research Coordination’
EUPHRESCO II	EC seventh framework programme ERA-Net project, the continuation of EUPHRESCO with more partners.
FP7	EU seventh framework programme for Research and Technological Development
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	Patent applications, patents, registered and unregistered design rights, copyrights, trade mark applications, trade marks, confidential information, trade secrets and any other similar proprietary rights for inventions, discoveries or technical information.
Pest	Any species, strain or biotype plant, animal or pathogenic agent injurious to plants or plant products [International Standard on Phytosanitary Measures No. 5, https://www.ippc.int/index.php?id=13399&tx_publication_pi1[showUid]=184195&frompage=13399&type=publication&subtype=&L=0#item] Here: including invasive non-native plants
Phytosanitary research	Research that deals with regulated quarantine pests, emerging pests with the potential to become quarantine pests (organisms new to countries, outbreaks in other countries, non-native invasive species relevant for or associated with, plants) and regulated non-quarantine pests (RNQP) in particular countries
Plant health	Regulated/statutory/quarantine plant health; all areas that come within the scope of the Community Plant Health Regime, e.g. pests (including pathogens and invasive weeds, GMO's are excluded. An equivalent term is ‘phytosanitary’.

Regulated pest	A regulated quarantine pest or a regulated non-quarantine pest [ISPM No. 5]
Research	Includes basic and applied research and experimental development as defined by the OECD (OECD Frascati manual, 2002). Activities excluded from the definition of research are also defined by the Frascati manual (pages 30–46)
Transnational phytosanitary projects	Projects on phytosanitary (regulated plant health) topics involving participants (funders or researchers) from more than one country that are initiated and funded via the EUPHRESKO network.

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Purpose and general provisions

- i. The purpose of this Modus Operandi is to specify the principles under which a sustainable long-term network will operate, to organise the management of the network, to define rights and obligations of the parties and to define principles of the implementation of transnational projects.
- i. EUPHRESKO is a network of phytosanitary research funders or programme managers in Europe and the EPPO region, including other countries as appropriate.
- ii. The network aims to enhance coordination and cooperation on phytosanitary research funding in the partner countries, and more widely as appropriate, thereby increasing the benefits from phytosanitary research for all partners. In particular, the outputs of this coordination and cooperation should contribute to:
 - Supporting EU plant health policy development and its implementation
 - Supporting the maintenance and development of phytosanitary science capability
 - Optimising and making best use of national funds for plant health research whilst avoiding duplication
 - Increase communication amongst partners and with other countries, relevant phytosanitary institutions and stakeholders on phytosanitary research.
- iii. The overarching aim is to help protect Europe's agriculture, horticulture, and forestry as well as plants in the environment, from regulated and emerging plant pests through effective trans-national research collaboration.
- iv. The Network will:
 - Identify and prioritise research needs for existing, new or emerging pests of statutory concern that can be addressed through transnational research (Common Strategic Research Agenda)
 - Implement transnational projects, disseminate research results and Network activities
 - Share information on national research projects and planning between Network Partners and other bodies as appropriate
 - Continue to advise the European Commission on plant health research priorities suitable for EU funding in the framework programs
 - Maintain and enhance linkages with official plant health bodies in the world, key stakeholders and relevant networks or working groups

Governing bodies, roles and responsibilities

Co-ordinator

- i. The Co-ordinator will act as head of the network and will be mainly responsible for:
 - External presentation of the Network
 - Transmission of any documents and information connected with the Network between the parties concerned
 - Calling of meetings of parties concerned
 - Publication of network documents
- ii. The function of the EUPHRESKO Co-ordinator will be taken over by the Network Secretariat at the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) for a minimum period of two years.
- iii. Continuation after the fixed period has to be decided by the Network Partners and the Governing Board before the end of the two years period.
- iv. The Co-ordinator shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other party.

Secretariat

- i. The Network Secretariat will be handled by the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) for a minimum period of two years.
- ii. The position of the Network Secretariat at EPPO is financed by a fixed payment of EUPHRESKO Partners for a minimum period of two years.
- iii. Continuation after the fixed period has to be decided by the Network Partners and the Governing Board before the end of the two years period.
- iv. The Secretariat will handle administrative work, including:
 - Assisting the Network Management Group (NMG) and EUPHRESKO Partners to coordinate phytosanitary research and facilitate trans-national collaboration and research projects
 - Hosting and updating of the EUPHRESKO homepage
 - Comprising the dissemination of important information, e.g. via newsletters, the EUPHRESKO homepage, through other EPPO activities (EPPO Workshops, Panels, etc) and EU-level fora (e.g. COPHS and SCPH)
 - Assisting in the organisation and facilitation of Network meetings and documentation (e.g. minutes, reporting) including reports for the EUPHRESKO Governing Board and its advisors, EPPO Council

- Assisting in updating of the Common Strategic Research Agenda and the maintenance of the EUPHRESKO databank on national phytosanitary research projects
- ii. The Secretariat duties concerning the initiation and implementation of transnational projects include:
 - Preparation of research initiation
 - Initial identification of topic suggestions
 - Coordination of the joining of the listed topic suggestions
 - Controlling of the establishment of the long list of topics
 - Coordination of the topic coordinator assignment
 - Giving administrative support to the production of the short topic description (e.g. providing tools)
 - Giving support to the establishment of funding consortia
 - Giving support to the decision and agreement of funding mechanisms
 - Giving support to the production and signing of commitments

Network Management Group

Composition of the Network Management Group

- i. The composition of the Network Management Group shall consist of the following members:
 - The Co-ordinator and Secretariat
 - Selected Network partners
- ii. The establishment of Network Management Group will be carried out by the Governing Board.
- iii. For a transition period, the members of the Network Management Group of the former ERA-Net EUPHRESKO II will stay in duty until otherwise decided by the Governing Board.
- iv. Any Network Management Group member may resign by delivering written notice to the Co-ordinator in consultation with their Governing Board Member. Such resignation shall be effective upon receipt unless it is specified to be effective at some other time or upon the happening of some other event.

Responsibility and Decision Making in the Network Management Group

- i. The Network Management Group shall be chaired by a member selected by the Network Management Group and confirmed by the Governing Board or by the Co-ordinator.

- ii. The Network Management Group shall meet once a year at the request of its chairperson or at any other time when necessary at the request of the majority of Network Management Group members. Meetings shall be convened by the chairperson with at least thirty (60) calendar days prior notice. This notice shall be accompanied by an agenda. The agenda shall be proposed by the chairperson. The agenda shall be deemed to have been accepted unless one of the Network Management Group members notifies the chairperson and the other Network Management Group members in writing of additional points to the agenda, at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting.
- iii. Minutes of the meetings of the Network Management Group shall be transmitted by the chairperson (or their representative) to the Network Management Group members within thirty (30) calendar days after the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within ten (10) calendar days from receipt, no Network Management Group member has objected in a traceable form to the chairperson. The exception shall be where a member has notified the chairperson in a traceable form of their absence during this period.
- iv. The agenda and the minutes of the meetings of the Network Management Group shall be transmitted by the chairperson (or their representative) to the Parties. The agenda shall be transmitted at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be transmitted within thirty (30) calendar days after the date of the meeting.
- v. Any decision requiring a vote at a Network Management Group meeting must be identified as such on the pre-meeting agenda, unless there is unanimous agreement to vote on a decision at that meeting and all Network Management Group members are present or represented.
- vi. However, any decision required to be taken by the Network Management Group may be taken in meetings held via teleconference and subsequently confirmed in written form. In addition, Network Management Group members may vote on a decision by email or by providing consent to a decision in writing via a signed undertaking, provided always that the number of votes is not less than the minimum number of votes that would be necessary to take such a decision at an actual meeting of the Network Management Group and that the required number of votes are received to make the vote quorate and that consent has been requested from all Network Management Group members.
- vii. The Network Management Group shall not deliberate and decide validly unless a majority of its members are present or represented ("quorate").

- viii. Each Network Management Group member shall have one (1) vote.
- ix. All decisions to be made by the Network Management Group shall be by consensus wherever possible, or if consensus cannot be reached, taken by the majority of the votes of the Network Management Group members present or represented by proxy at a quorate meeting, provided always that a Network Management Group member who represents a Party whose scope of work, time for performance, costs or liabilities are changed or whose information is to be published, disclosed or Disseminated or whose legitimate business interests may be affected or whose name is to be included in a press release, may veto such decisions.

Responsibilities of the Network Management Group

- i. Making proposals to the Governing Board for the launching of transnational projects.
- ii. Keeping the direct contact to advisors.
- iii. Initiating the maintenance and updating of the Common Strategic Research Agenda that will reflect national research agendas of the Network Partners. It will constitute the actual status quo on phytosanitary research needs and gaps.
- iv. Initiating the maintenance and updating of the database on national phytosanitary research projects, which gives an overview on national phytosanitary projects in the partner countries including the annual budget.
- v. Initiating to advise the European Commission on plant health priorities in their framework programs according to the mandate given to EUPHRESKO by the Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS) in June 2007.
- vi. Initiating periodic evaluation of the Network and its activities.
- vii. Establishing linkages to other networks, ERA-NETs or other plant health organisations e.g. USDA, CABI etc. These contacts are not restricted to plant health but might comprise a broad range of disciplines and research sectors. In addition the consortium should seek regular contact with organisations who are not yet members of EUPHRESKO, e.g. in third countries such as the USA (and the wider QUAD of Australia, New Zealand, Canada and the USA), Africa and Asia.
- viii. Initiation of the further development of the Network's homepage. The website shall offer possibilities for publication of research results from transnational projects and information on all network activities including identified topics and topic descriptions.
- ix. This list is not exclusive and might be modified with different or additional activities as needed.

Governing Board

Composition of the Governing Board

- i. The Governing Board (GB) will be composed of duly authorised representatives of the ministry from each Network Partner or any other authorised person from the Partner organisation.
- ii. After having informed the others in writing, each GB member shall have the right to replace its representative and/or to appoint a proxy although it shall use all reasonable endeavours to maintain the continuity of its representation.
- iii. Each representative shall name an alternative representative.

Decision Making in the Governing Board

- i. The Governing Board shall be chaired by a selected representative.
- ii. The Governing Board shall meet at the request of its chairperson or at any other time when necessary at the request of one of the GB members. Meetings shall be convened by the chairperson with at least thirty (30) calendar days prior notice. This notice shall be accompanied by an agenda. The agenda shall be proposed by the chairperson. The agenda shall be deemed to be accepted unless one of the GB members notifies the chairperson and the other GB members in writing of additional points to the agenda, at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting.
- iii. Minutes of the meetings of the Governing Board shall be transmitted to the GB members within thirty (30) calendar days after the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted by the other GB members if, within ten (10) calendar days from receipt, no GB member has objected in a traceable form to the chairperson.
- iv. Any decision requiring a vote at a GB meeting must be identified as such on the pre-meeting agenda, unless there is unanimous agreement to vote on a decision at that meeting and all GB members are present or represented.
- v. However, any decision required to be taken by the GB may be taken in meetings held via teleconference and subsequently confirmed in written form. In addition, GB members may vote on a decision by email or by providing consent to a decision in writing via a signed undertaking, provided always that the number of votes is not less than the minimum number of votes that would be necessary to take such a decision at an actual meeting of the GB and that the required number of votes are received to make the vote quorate and that consent has been requested from all GB members.

- vi. The Governing Board shall not deliberate and decide validly unless the majority of its members are present or represented. Where decisions are to be taken unanimously, all Governing Board members must be represented at the meeting
- vii. Decisions shall be by consensus wherever possible, or if consensus cannot be reached, taken by the majority of the votes of the Governing Board present or represented by proxy at a quorate meeting, provided always that any member of the Governing Board who represents a Network Partner who will be concerned by the decision may veto such decisions.
- viii. In voting each member of the Governing Board shall have one vote.

Responsibilities of the Governing Board

The Governing Board shall be responsible for:

- Deciding whether or not to accept proposals made by the Network Management Group for launching of transnational projects
- Deciding on publications referred to from the Network Management Group

- In the event of a dispute between Network Partners that cannot be settled amicably between the Parties concerned, the Governing Board can intervene in an attempt to resolve the dispute. A member of the Governing Board who is associated with any of the Parties in dispute shall not participate in its deliberations or vote on its decision, but can to the extent such decision affects their legitimate interests, veto such decision. In the event that no resolution to the dispute is agreed through Governing Board intervention, the Parties in dispute may invoke the dispute resolution procedure as indicated in Section VII.5

Kommentar [s1]: Do we need such a paragraph on disputes?

Advisors

- i. The Network is expected to establish contact with organisations which influence plant health policy and with decision makers which should have input into the Network's activities, such organisations will be referred to as Advisors.
- ii. The circle of Advisors might be composed of:
 - Directorate General of Health and Consumers Protection
 - Directorate General of Research
 - Standing Committee of Plant Health
 - European Food Safety Authority
 - Chief Officers of Plant Health Services
- i. This list can be extended if appropriate.

- ii. Advisors might influence Network activities and might participate in Network meetings and can be included in all communication flows.
- iii. Advisors can be asked for advise on Network activities, as transnational research projects or dissemination activities
- iv. Advisors should be informed on important consortium activities and decisions

Network Partner's roles and responsibilities

Composition of the Network

- i. The Network will consist of Partners who represent phytosanitary research funders or programme managers in Europe, including other such bodies in third countries as appropriate.
- ii. This refers mainly to ministries, governmental bodies or research institutions with their own research budgets but not to private organisations or enterprises.

Roles and Responsibilities

- i. Partners have to finance their own participation in the consortium without entitlement to funding by any other party.
- ii. Partners will have complete access to all information and might participate in all discussions on topics and topic descriptions.
- iii. Partners should actively contribute to the Network and its activities by participating in transnational research projects
- iv. Partners shall ensuring contact with their own national stakeholders, e.g. via workshops, to provide contributions to the Common Strategic Research Agenda

Decision making in the Network

- i. The Network Partners shall meet at the request of the Co-ordinator or at any other time when necessary at the request of the Governing Board or Network Management Group members. Meetings shall be convened by the chairperson with at least thirty (30) calendar days prior notice. This notice shall be accompanied by an agenda. The agenda shall be proposed by the Co-ordinator. The agenda shall be deemed to be accepted unless one of the Network Partners notifies the Co-ordinator and the other Network Partners in writing of additional points to the agenda, at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting.

- ii. Minutes of the meetings shall be transmitted to the Network Partners within thirty (30) calendar days after the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted by the Network Partners if, within ten (10) calendar days from receipt, no Network Partner has objected in a traceable form to the Co-ordinator.
- iii. Any decision requiring a vote during a Network meeting must be identified as such on the pre-meeting agenda, unless there is unanimous agreement to vote on a decision at that meeting and all Network Partners are present or represented.
- iv. However, any decision required to be taken by the Network Partners may be taken in meetings held via teleconference and subsequently confirmed in written form. In addition, Network Partners members may vote on a decision by email or by providing consent to a decision in writing via a signed undertaking, provided always that the number of votes is not less than the minimum number of votes that would be necessary to take such a decision at an actual meeting of the Network Partners and that the required number of votes are received to make the vote quorate and that consent has been requested from all Network Partners.
- v. Network Partners will have one voice if decisions of all parties are required; unanimity is favoured but not mandatory.
- vi. Decisions on routine issues can be made by the Network Management Group, with the agreement of all Network Partners.

Research Co-operation

- i. The initiation, planning, funding and realisation of trans-national projects will be the main task of the EUPHRESKO Network and will be mainly assisted by the Network Secretariat.
- ii. The process starts with the identification of relevant topics for transnational phytosanitary research in compliance with the EUPHRESKO standards.
- iii. Topics should have a definite reference to phytosanitary problems and must be accomplishable in a period of one to three years and with the allocated funds. Doubling with topics of the EU framework programmes must be avoided.
- iv. Funders of at least two different countries have to participate in a topic that will be accomplished under the EUPHRESKO Network.
- v. Topic identification might start any time, as needed, but should aim to be done at least once year as part of a regular routine. Periods and frequency of topic

identification processes should comply with needs in the plant health sector and accord to the situation.

- vi. Topics can be proposed by any Network Partner, Governing Board member or an Advisor and will be published on the Network Homepage.
- vii. Interested funders have to decide on a topic coordinator, who will be responsible for the initiation of the development of an appropriate topic description. The topic description should identify the problem and the outcomes required, but not the methods or approaches. The finalised topic description will be published on the Network Homepage to enable funders to decide on a participation in the project.
- viii. The following initiation process of transnational projects will be open to all interested parties. Interested funders are requested to get in contact with the topic coordinator to form a funders' consortium. The number of funders involved will not be limited. Interested funders do not have to be Network Partners.
- ix. The funding mechanism, e.g. real-common pot, virtual-common pot or non-competitive mechanism, and the project budget will be determined by the funders involved.
- x. The implementation of the individual trans-national projects will not be steered by the consortium. It will be solely the responsibility of interested funders (funding consortium).
- xi. The toolbox and all necessary information and documents for the initiation and implementation of transnational projects that had been developed in the ERA-Net EUPHRESKO will stay available on the Network Homepage.
- xii. Results from transnational projects initiated by the EUPHRESKO Network should be made accessible to all Network Partners as soon as possible.
- xiii. Network Partners commit themselves not to publish any results before a given period of time, to enable the research consortium to produce an official publication.

IPR & Publications

Intellectual Property Rights

Ownership of IP

Each Party shall retain ownership of its own Pre-Existing Know-How developed prior to entering into a transnational project.

Knowledge shall be the property of the Party performing the work leading to the development of that Knowledge.

Joint Ownership

If, in the course of carrying out work on a transnational project, a joint invention, design or work is made (and more than one Party is contributor to it), and if the features of such joint invention design or work are such that it is not possible to separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining and/or maintaining the relevant patent protection or any other intellectual property right, the Parties concerned agree that they may jointly apply to obtain and/or maintain the relevant right. The Parties concerned shall seek to agree between themselves arrangements for applying for, obtaining and maintaining such rights on a case-by-case basis.

Where there are several co-owners, the Parties concerned may for administrative purposes assign ownership to a single Party. This could be affected by a joint ownership agreement between all of the Parties. Such an agreement must set out how issues such as decision making in relation to the Knowledge and sharing of costs and revenue from exploitation of the Knowledge are to be dealt with.

Publications

Publications

- i. In publications proper references to the all participating parties and to the EUPHRESKO Network shall be made.
- ii. For the avoidance of doubt it is stated that unless otherwise agreed between the parties concerned no party shall have the right to publish or allow the publication of data which includes knowledge of another party, pre-existing know-how of another party or confidential information of another party even where such data is amalgamated with such first party's knowledge, pre-existing know-how or other information, document or material.
- iii. All authors are required to indicate their membership of EUPHRESKO in all publications and communications relating to transnational projects.

